

Jute Fibre Gradation by Hybrid AHP-TOPSIS Methodology of Multi-Criteria Decision Making Technique

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Abstract

Amongst the various exponents of Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques, the hybrid AHP-TOPSIS approach is much more robust-yet-flexible paradigm in any case of decision-making problem. This methodology is based on strong mathematical foundation of both AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) and TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solutions). Gradation of jute fibres on the basis of certain quantitative as well as subjective parameters or attributes is done by traditional method which follows the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) gradation system. In this paper a modified approach has been proposed using hybrid AHP-TOPSIS tool for ranking/gradation and thereby selection of jute fibres on the basis of some apposite selection criteria like fibre strength, root content, fibre defects, fibre colour, bulk density and fibre fineness. It is found that the orders of preference of the top-ranked and worst-ranked jute fibre varieties/samples exactly match with the traditional BIS system and MAHP approach done by an earlier researcher. Moreover, the new hybrid approach shows an overall good agreement in terms of ranking with the previous system or approach.

Keywords

AHP, Jute Gradation, MCDM, TOPSIS.

1. Introduction

The experiences of the domain experts play an important role during the gradation of jute fibres. In some cases, it is done using BIS method [1-2]. In BIS method, which is a scientific grading system introduced by Bureau of Indian Standards in 1969, eight grades are used to be identified initially based on seven jute fibre parameters. However, in the modern BIS jute grading system, eight jute grades are identified on the basis of only six physical parameters or attributes of jute fibres namely strength (tenacity), root content, defects, fineness, colour and (bulk) density. In the present BIS system, jute gradation is primarily done using a scoring system of the above mentioned six fibre parameters, and this is done as per IS: 271 - 2003 standard where different score marks has been stipulated for each grade [1]. Choudhuri [2] considered above mentioned six jute fibre parameters as six decision criteria and presented

an alternative approach for jute fibre gradation or ranking with the help of Multiplicative Analytic Hierarchy Process (MAHP).

Amongst the various exponents of MCDM technique, the AHP is one of the widely used and most talked about approach which can efficiently handle both the tangible and the intangible attributes. According to AHP method, in a decision-making problem with M alternatives and N criteria, the total number of pair-wise comparison matrices is expressed by the following expression :

$$\frac{N(N-1)}{2} + N \cdot \frac{M(M-1)}{2}$$

which may be practically unmanageable in situations where a large number of decision criteria and alternatives are involved.

TOPSIS, on the contrary, is more efficient in handling the tangible attributes and there is no limitation of the number of decision criteria or alternatives. Hence, in this paper, a maiden endeavour has been made using

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AHP-TOPSIS hybrid method/approach for solving the same problem (i.e. gradation and selection of jute fibres) using the same data set employed by Choudhuri [2], and the efficacy of the proposed method has been evaluated with respect to the earlier methods/approaches using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

2. AHP-TOPSIS Hybrid Methodology

The AHP was invented by T.L. Saaty [3-8], and it is based on the formation of pair-wise comparison matrix to extract relative weights of criteria and scores of alternatives. The TOPSIS was developed by Hwang and Yoon [9], the basic philosophy of which is that the selected alternative/option should have the shortest distance, in a geometrical sense, from the positive ideal solution (PIS) and longest distance from the negative ideal solution (NIS) or worst solution. In the case of AHP-TOPSIS hybrid approach, on the other hand, the pair-wise comparison method of AHP is amalgamated with the other steps of TOPSIS. The below is explained the fundamental steps involved in the AHP-TOPSIS hybrid approach [10]:

Step 1 :

The relevant goal or objective, the decision criteria and the alternatives of the problem are identified.

Step 2 :

A decision matrix of criteria and alternatives are produced, in this step, basis the information available regarding the problem in hand. If number of alternatives is M and number of criteria is N, then the resultant decision matrix with an order of M x N can be represented as under:

$$D (M \times N) = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1N} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2N} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{M1} & x_{M2} & \dots & x_{MN} \end{bmatrix}$$

where the element x_{ij} denotes the actual value of i^{th} alternative w.r.t. j^{th} decision attribute.

Table 2.1 : The fundamental 9-Point relational scale proposed by T.L. Saaty [3]

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective.
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgement slightly favour one activity over another.
5	Essential or strong importance	Experience and judgement strongly favour one activity over another.
7	Very strong importance	An activity is very strongly favoured and its dominance is demonstrated.
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favouring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation.
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values between two adjacent judgement	When compromise is needed.
Reciprocals	If activity p has one of the above numbers assigned to it when compared with activity q, then q has the reciprocal value when compared with p.	

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Step 3 :

In this step, the decision matrix is converted to a normalized decision matrix so that the scores obtained in different scales become comparable. An element R_{ij} of the normalized decision matrix is calculated by Eq. (1):

$$R_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{[\sum_i^M = 1(x_{ij})^2]^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

Step 4 :

In this step, the relative importance of different criteria with respect to the objective of the problem and the scores of alternatives with respect to each of the criteria is determined by using a 9-Point scale of relative importance proposed by Saaty, which is shown in Table 2.1. For N criteria the size of the comparison matrix (P_1) will be $N \times N$ and the entry c_{ij} will denote the relative importance of criterion i with respect to the criterion j . In the matrix,

$$c_{ij} = 1, \text{ for } i=j \text{ and } c_{ji} = \frac{1}{c_{ij}} \text{ for } i \neq j.$$

The pair-wise comparison matrix can be represented as follows:

$$P_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1N} \\ c_{21} & 1 & \dots & c_{2N} \\ \dots & \dots & 1 & \dots \\ c_{N1} & c_{N2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The relative weight or importance of the i^{th} criteria (W_i) is determined by calculating the geometric mean (GM) of the i^{th} row and then normalizing the geometric means of rows of the above matrix. This can be represented by the Eq. (2) and Eq. (3):

$$GM_i = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^N c_{ij} \right\}^{\frac{1}{N}} \quad (2)$$

and

$$W_i = \frac{GM_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N GM_i} \quad (3)$$

Then matrix P_3 and P_4 are calculated such that $P_3 = P_1 \times P_2$ and $P_4 = P_3 / P_2^T$, where $P_2 = [W_1 \ W_2 \ \dots \ W_N]^T$

In order to check the consistency or validity of pairwise comparison, at first the principal Eigen Vector (λ_{max})

of the original pairwise comparison matrix (P_1) is derived from the average of matrix P_4 . Afterwards, consistency index (I_C) and consistency ratio (R_C) are determined using Eq. (4) and Eq. (5), respectively:

$$I_C = \frac{\lambda_{max} - N}{N - 1} \quad (4)$$

and

$$R_C = \frac{I_C}{RCI} \quad (5)$$

where RCI is random consistency index whose values are given in Table 2.2. The judgement is considered to be consistent and hence acceptable only if the value of R_C is less than or equal to 0.1. Otherwise, the pair-wise comparison matrix has to be reconstructed by reconsidering the entries of the matrix.

Table 2.2: RCI values for different numbers of attributes or criteria (N)

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
RCI	0	0	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45

Step 5 :

The weighted normalized matrix is obtained by multiplying each column of the normalized decision matrix R by the associated criteria weight corresponding to that column. Hence, an element v_{ij} of weighted normalized matrix V can be represented by Eq. (6):

$$v_{ij} = W_j \cdot R_{ij} \quad (6)$$

Step 6 :

In this step, the positive ideal solution (A^*) and negative ideal solution (A^-) are generated in the following manner:

$$A^* = \{(\max v_{ij} / j \in J), (\min v_{ij} / j \in J') \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M\} \\ = \{v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_N^+\}$$

$$A^- = \{(\min v_{ij} / j \in J), (\max v_{ij} / j \in J') \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M\} \\ = \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_N^-\}$$

where $J = \{j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N / j \text{ associated with benefit or positive criteria}\}$

and $J' = \{j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N / j \text{ associated with cost or negative criteria}\}$

For the benefit criteria (higher-the-better type), the decision maker wants to have the maximum value among the alternatives. So, A^* indicates the positive ideal solution (PIS). On the contrary, for the cost criteria (lower-the-better type), the decision maker wants to have the minimum value amongst the alternatives., and hence, A^- indicates the negative ideal solution (NIS).

Step 7

The N dimensional Euclidean distance method is applied in this case, to measure the separation distances of each alternative from PIS and NIS.

$$D_i^* = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^N (v_{ij} - v_j^*)^2 \right\}^{1/2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, M$$

and

$$D_i^- = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^N (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2 \right\}^{1/2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, M$$

where D_i^* and D_i^- are the separation distances of alternative i from the PIS and NIS, respectively.

Step 8

In this step, the relative closeness or degree of closeness (C_i^*) of each alternative with respect to PIS is derived using Eq. (7). Noteworthy to mention, here, that the value of C_i^* ranges from 0 to 1.

$$C_i^* = \frac{D_i^-}{(D_i^* + D_i^-)}$$

Step 9

All the alternatives are now arranged in descending order of magnitude of C_i^* . The higher the C_i^* value the better the ranking. Hence, the alternative at the top of the list is the most preferred one and vice versa.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Data Collection and Analysis

The test results of nine jute fibre varieties or samples with respect to six fibre parameters like bundle strength (tenacity), root content, defects, fibre fineness, fibre colour and bulk density, as well as fibre gradation as per existing BIS grading system have been collected from National Institute of Research on Jute and Allied Fibre Technology (NIRJAFT) and furnished in Table 3. As mentioned earlier, the same data set were used by Choudhuri [2] for his gradation approach through MAHP.

In BIS gradation system, attributes like fibre colour and bulk density are assessed subjectively. However, in order to facilitate numerical calculations, these subjective attributes or criteria should be assigned numerical values. The same assignment conversion as employed by Choudhuri [2] in his approach, is adopted in this case also to keep parity in the original data set. Hence, the 'Fair good' and 'Fair average' colour attributes have been assigned numerical values 3 and 2 respectively, and two density attributes namely 'Medium bodied' and 'Heavy bodied' have been assigned values 2 and 3 respectively, as shown within small brackets alongwith corresponding attributes in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 : Original data set containing jute fibre properties and BIS gradation [2]

Sample no.	Tenacity (g/tex)	Root content (%)	Defects (%)	Fineness (tex)	Colour	Density	BIS Grade
1	24.2	10	1.5	2.9	Fair good (3)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4 + 60% ↑
2	26.5	8	1.5	3.2	Fair good (3)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4 + 80% ↑
3	23.1	8	1.5	3.0	Fair good (3)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4 + 65% ↑
4	24.1	8	2.0	3.3	Fair good (3)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4 + 20% ↑
5	27.1	8	2.0	2.9	Fair average (2)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4 + 35% ↑
6	21.0	15	1.5	3.0	Fair average (2)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-4
7	18.8	10	2.0	3.5	Fair average (2)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-5 + 20% ↑
8	22.4	10	2.0	3.1	Fair average (2)	Medium bodied (2)	TD-5 + 60% ↑
9	15.5	15	1.0	2.6	Fair average (2)	Heavy bodied (3)	TD-5 + 80% ↑

3.2 AHP-TOPSIS Approach for Jute Fibre Gradation

It has been already observed that the problem of jute fibre gradation and selection in order to determine the quality value of different jute fibre varieties can be formulated as an MCDM problem as envisaged by Choudhuri [2]. In this paper, the same jute fibre gradation problem has been considered, which consists of nine jute fibre varieties/samples to be evaluated (using hybrid AHP-TOPSIS approach) with respect to six jute fibre criteria or parameters, namely bundle strength (BS), fibre defects (FD), root content (RC), fibre fineness (FF), fibre colour (FC), and bulk density (BD). The data set for developing the related decision matrix for this gradation problem are shown in Table 3 which also shows the gradation as per existing BIS system. It is obviously a challenging decision making problem since the values of the criteria or parameters under consideration are not only quite close to each other but conflicting, too. These values of jute fibre properties (or criteria) have been employed to derive the quality index (C_i^*) of individual jute fibre variety/sample using hybrid AHP-TOPSIS approach.

In order to determine the quality indices/values of different jute fibre varieties, which is the goal of the present decision making situation, the same type of hierarchy formulation as proposed by Choudhuri [2] is adopted here also, as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure3.1: Hierarchy of jute fibre properties

3.3 Determining criteria weights or priority weights

The pair-wise comparison matrix of the six decision criteria with regard to overall goal of the problem is presented in Table 3.2. The pair-wise comparison amongst different criteria has been done on the basis of Saaty's 9-Point Relational Scale presented in Table 2.1.

While making pair-wise comparison, the parameter bundle strength (BS) has been assigned moderate importance over fibre fineness (FF), essential/strong importance over fibre defects (FD), and very strong importance over root content (RC). Moreover, the relative importance of parameter 'BS' over bulk density (BD) is between strong and very strong, and that over criterion fibre colour (FC) is between very strong and extreme. The other pair-wise comparisons have been made, likewise.

Table 3.2 : Pair-wise comparison matrix and global weights of criteria w.r.t. goal

Criteria	BS	FC	BD	RC	FD	FF	Geometric Mean (GM) of Criteria	Normalized GM [global weights]
BS	1	8	6	7	5	3	4.1407	0.4809
FC	1/8	1	2	1/3	1/4	1/3	0.4368	0.0507
BD	1/6	1/2	1	1/2	1/4	1/2	0.4163	0.0484
RC	1/7	3	2	1	1/4	1/2	0.6892	0.0800
D	1/5	4	4	4	1	4	1.9270	0.2238
FF	1/3	3	2	2	1/4	1	1.0000	0.1161

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$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 8 & 6 & 7 & 5 & 3 \\ 1/8 & 1 & 2 & 1/3 & 1/4 & 1/3 \\ 1/6 & 1/2 & 1 & 1/2 & 1/4 & 1/2 \\ 1/7 & 3 & 2 & 1 & 1/4 & 1/2 \\ 1/5 & 4 & 4 & 4 & 1 & 4 \\ 1/3 & 3 & 2 & 2 & 1/4 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0.4809 \\ 0.0507 \\ 0.0484 \\ 0.0800 \\ 0.2238 \\ 0.1161 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.2047 \\ 0.3289 \\ 0.3079 \\ 0.5117 \\ 1.5011 \\ 0.7414 \end{bmatrix}$$

Here,

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{(3.2047 + 0.3289 + 0.3079 + 0.5117 + 1.5011 + 0.7414)}{(0.4809 + 0.0507 + 0.0484 + 0.0800 + 0.2238 + 0.1161)} / 6 = 6.4996$$

$$\text{Hence, } I_c = \frac{6.4996 - 6}{6 - 1} = 0.0999$$

$$\text{and, } R_c = \frac{I_c}{RCI} = \frac{0.0999}{1.24} = 0.08058 < 0.1$$

Since, the consistency ratio (R_c) is well below 0.1, so the judgement of the pair-wise comparison is consistent and hence acceptable. The values of normalized GMs represent the relative importance of the criteria with respect to the overall objective, and since there is no sub-criterion of any of the main criterion, the relative importances of the considered criteria indicate their global weights with respect to the objective. Therefore, the global weights of strength (BS), colour (FC), density (BD), root content (RC), defects (D) and fineness (FF) are 0.4809, 0.0507, 0.0484, 0.0800, 0.2238, and 0.1161 respectively. It should be noted here that BS, FC and BD are all benefit criteria (higher-the-better type) since they do exert a positive influence on the

goal, whereas RC, D and FF are cost criteria (lower-the-better type) having a negative influence on the overall goal.

Table 4.1: Normalized decision matrix of criteria

Sample No.	Normalized Decision Matrix of Criteria					
	BS	FC	BD	RC	D	FF
1	0.3540	0.4009	0.3123	0.3153	0.2942	0.3153
2	0.3877	0.4009	0.3123	0.2522	0.2942	0.3480
3	0.3379	0.4009	0.3123	0.2522	0.2942	0.3262
4	0.3525	0.4009	0.3123	0.2522	0.3922	0.3588
5	0.3964	0.2673	0.3123	0.2522	0.3922	0.3153
6	0.3072	0.2673	0.3123	0.4729	0.2942	0.3262
7	0.2750	0.2673	0.3123	0.3153	0.3922	0.3806
8	0.3277	0.2673	0.3123	0.3153	0.3922	0.3371
9	0.2267	0.2673	0.4685	0.4729	0.1961	0.2827

4. Results and Discussion

Once the global weights or priority weights of different criteria with respect to the objective of the problem were determined as shown in Table 3.2, the other steps of AHP-TOPSIS method were followed as chalked out earlier (from Step 5 to Step 9) for calculating quality index of jute fibre varieties (alternatives).

Table 4.2: Salient results of AHP-TOPSIS alongwith quality index (Ci*) and ranking of alternatives

Sample No.	Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix of Criteria						D_i^*	D_i^-	C_i^*	Rank
	BS	FC	BD	RC	D	FF				
1	0.1702	0.0203	0.0151	0.0252	0.0658	0.0366	0.0315	0.0670	0.6800	2
2	0.1864	0.0203	0.0151	0.0202	0.0658	0.0404	0.0248	0.0827	0.7695	1
3	0.1625	0.0203	0.0151	0.0202	0.0658	0.0379	0.0368	0.0611	0.6241	4
4	0.1695	0.0203	0.0151	0.0202	0.0878	0.0417	0.0501	0.0634	0.5589	5
5	0.1906	0.0136	0.0151	0.0202	0.0878	0.0366	0.0452	0.0838	0.6497	3
6	0.1477	0.0136	0.0151	0.0379	0.0658	0.0379	0.0526	0.0449	0.4608	7
7	0.1323	0.0136	0.0151	0.0252	0.0878	0.0442	0.0748	0.0264	0.2611	9
8	0.1576	0.0136	0.0151	0.0252	0.0878	0.0392	0.0565	0.0504	0.4717	6
9	0.1090	0.0136	0.0227	0.0379	0.0439	0.0328	0.0838	0.0460	0.3543	8

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The determination of normalized decision matrix (as shown in Table 4.1) and weighted normalized decision matrix were done in accordance with the method described earlier. After the determination of positive ideal solution (PIS) and negative ideal solution (NIS) corresponding to each criterion, the separation distances of alternatives from the PIS (Di^*) and that from the NIS (Di) were calculated. Table 4.2 reveals the salient results of AHP-TOPSIS analysis. The values of relative closeness indices (Ci^*) for 9 jute fibre alternatives are depicted in Figure 4.1. It is observed that the best alternative is sample no 2 with a Ci^* value of 0.7695 being close to 1, whereas the worst choice is jute fibre sample no 7 with a Ci^* value of 0.2611 which is close to zero.

Figure 4.1: Relative closeness values (or quality indices) of jute fibres

The comparison of ranking orders obtained by earlier methods and the proposed AHP-TOPSIS-based approach is furnished in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 : Comparison of ranking orders of different models

Sample No.	BIS ranking	MAHP ranking [2]	AHP-[2]TOPSIS ranking
1	3	4	2
2	1	1	1
3	2	2	4
4	5	5	5
5	4	3	3
6	6	7	7
7	9	9	9
8	8	6	6
9	7	8	8

It is found from Table 4.3 that, for all the three approaches or ranking methods, jute fibre samples 2 and 7 occupy the same position in the ranking patterns -- rank 1 (best choice) and rank 9 (worst choice), respectively. There are slight discrepancies, however, in some of the intermediate rankings. The possible cause of these discrepancies may be attributed to the different approaches of ranking the alternatives in two methods. Nevertheless, it has been found that the differences/discrepancies in ranking patterns of the two methods (BIS and AHP-TOPSIS) are not statistically significant (vide Appendix I for statistical analysis).

Table 4.4 : Comparison of different methods using Spearman's rank correlation coefficients

Method	BIS Grading System	MAHP	AHP-TOPSIS
BIS Grading System	-	0.9333	0.9000
MAHP	-	0.9333	
AHP-TOPSIS	-	-	-

In order to check the validity and efficacy of the proposed decision making model, a comparison of ranking performances obtained by earlier methods and that attained by the proposed model is presented in Table 4.4, on the basis of Spearman's Rank Correlation analysis which is given by Eq. (8):

$$R_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^M D_i}{M(M^2-1)}$$

where R_s is Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, Di is absolute difference between rankings obtained by any two methods, and M is the total number of decision alternatives, which is 9 in this case.

Very high Spearman's rank correlation coefficients of 0.9000 between existing BIS system and AHP-TOPSIS-based ranking, and that of 0.9333 between MAHP ranking done by Choudhuri [2] and the proposed AHP-TOPSIS model corroborates the potential applicability of the proposed model in gradation and ranking of the candidate jute fibre samples (varieties) thereby identifying the choice for specific end-use requirements.

It is worth mentioning at this juncture that the entire analysis has been performed using *MCDM Plus*, a self-developed user-friendly software developed using *MATLAB2015* programming platform.

5. Conclusion

A new approach of MCDM technique has been demonstrated to evaluate the quality index of jute fibre varieties, there by ranking and grading the candidate jute fibres in terms of applicability towards specific end-use. All the jute fibre properties or attributes were given commensurate weights based on their influence on overall objective. The final raking of 9 jute fibre varieties was elicited by the proposed approach which amalgamates the principles of two popular exponents of MCDM, namely AHP and TOPSIS. The ranking or gradation of jute fibres attained by this hybrid method corroborates a very good degree of agreement with existing BIS gradation system and MAHP approach done by an earlier researcher. Free from ranking inconsistencies (associated with AHP method alone), the AHP-TOPSIS hybrid approach exploits the experience of the domain experts to construct the pairwise comparison matrix, which can be modified very easily in new situation. Thus, thenew approach is a flexible-yet-potent way of decision-making and can be applied in any such situation regardless of fibre types.

Appendix I

Statistical F-Test Analysis to Compare Rankings of BIS and AHP-TOPSIS Methods

BIS Method	: Variance in rankings (σ_1) = 7.5
	Sample size (n_1) = 9
AHP-TOPSIS Method	: Variance in rankings (σ_1) = 7.5
	Sample size (n_2) = 9

Step-1 : Stating the Hypotheses

Null hypothesis (H_0) : difference in ranking patterns not statistically significant.

Alternative hypothesis (H_a) : difference in ranking patterns statistically significant.

Step-2 : Finding the Calculated F Value

$$F_{\text{Calculated}} = \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \frac{7.5}{7.5} = 1$$

Step-3: Calculation of Degrees of Freedom (df)

Degrees of freedom for BIS method (df_1) = 9-1 = 8

Degrees of freedom for AHP-TOPSIS method (df_2) = 9-1=8

Step-4 : Selection of the Level of Significance (α -level)

Let us choose the standard - level of 0.05.

Step-5 : Finding the Critical F Value from the F-Table

For $df_1 = df_2 = 8$, with $\alpha = 0.05$, the critical F value can be found as:

$$F_{8,8,0.05} = 3.44$$

Step-6 : Statistical Inference Through Comparison of F Values

Since, $F_{\text{Calculated}} \ll F_{\text{Critical}}$,

so, we cannot reject the null hypothesis (H_0), i.e. H_0 is true.

In other words, there is enough evidence (with 95% confidence) that the difference in ranking patterns (given by BIS and AHP-TOPSIS methods) are not statistically significant.

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